

Password Security using BCrypt

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Abstract—Passwords are still the most prevalent means of user identification for many internet services, and assaults on password databases constitute a serious concern. Servers maintain password hashes produced using special password hashing techniques to slow down guessing attempts and so lessen the risk. BCrypt is a password hashing algorithm that converts variable-length input into fixed-length output. It's known as hashing. The bcrypt algorithm is used to hash the input. PBKDF2, bcrypt, and scrypt are the most commonly used functions of this type. In today's environment, we rely on Internet services on a regular basis.

Keywords—*bcrypt algorithm, sal, hash*

I. INTRODUCTION

BCrypt is a password-hashing function developed by Niels Provos and David Mazières and first presented at USENIX in 1999. b for Blowfish and crypt for the name of the hashing function used by the UNIX password system. [1]. We can use the bcrypt hashing function to create a password security platform that scales with computing power and always hashes each password with a salt. BCrypt has the advantage of requiring a salt by default.

If a password is stored in plain text or is compromised by a simple encryption method, the password can be decrypted and stolen. It could lead to a forged login and a breach of privacy [2]. BCrypt may adjust the cost of hashing by utilising a Key Factor. The hash output can be changed by changing Key Factors. As a result, BCrypt is impervious to hackers, particularly the rainbow table method of password cracking. If you have sensitive data or information that needs to be protected, it's critical that you secure it properly. As we've seen, there are a variety of password approaches for securing this information, but only BCrypt provides a genuinely strong solution [3].

All an attacker needs to do if they get their hands on my user's password digest is run the hash function against a large number of probable passwords. The time it takes to run that code millions of times is the only thing standing between the attacker and my original password. By imposing a cost factor on the hash, also known as salt rounds, we may effectively slow down the attacker. The internal hashing procedure will be repeated as many times as the cost factor specifies. The hashing process slows down by a factor of two for every additional cost component. Even if the attacker obtains our password digest, the hash function will run as slowly as the number of salt rounds we

specify. You can delay the process down as much as you want, which was a unique feature of bcrypt [4].

1.1 BCrypt alternatives

Password hashing function is not limited to BCrypt. Look at other solutions and competing choices. When comparing BCrypt alternatives, keep features and functioning in mind. Some of the BCrypt alternatives are listed below:

1. MD5: The MD5 hashing method is a one-way cryptographic function that takes any length message as input and produces a fixed-length digest value that can be used to verify the original message. [5].

2. SHA1: The Secure Hash Algorithm 1 (SHA-1) is a cryptographic computer security algorithm.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

P. Sriamya and R. A. Karthika in "Providing password security by salted password hashing using BCrypt algorithm" focuses on providing security to user's data by using Salted Password Hashing Technique. Also, they discussed how to prevent several password attacks [2].

In "A comparison of password protection method for web-based platforms implemented with PHP and MYSQL" by Nedyalko Katrandzhiev, Daniel Hristozov and Borislav Milenkov explains the need of using security methods to protect your sensitive data. Here they compare MD5, SHA1, BCrypt and Argon2. From this we understood that BCrypt is better compared to MD5 and SHA1 [6].

In "Password security using BCrypt with AES encryption Algorithm" by Narander Kumar and Priyanka Chaudhary tells about technique utilizing BCrypt technique with AES encryption for users account protection [7].

Niels Provos and David Mazières in "A Future Adaptable Password Scheme" suggest methods for designing systems that keep password security up to date with hardware speeds. They conclude that BCrypt, a hash function, can be used to replace the UNIX password hashing algorithm or as a front-end to secure password protocols such as SRP [8].

We may conclude from all of the aforementioned papers that BCrypt is one of the best data protection methods. By raising the amount of rounds of bcrypt, we can reduce any advantages attackers would gain from faster hardware.

III. METHODOLOGY

Hashing a password

Taking a plain text password and running it through a hash algorithm is known as "hashing." The hash algorithm accepts any length string and returns a fixed length string. Every time you password into the hash algorithm, the returned hash is the same [9].

Salting a password

The hash algorithm's result is no longer predictable after hashing a plain text password with a salt. The hash generated by the same password will no longer be the same. The salt is included in the hash by default. [9].

How to salt & hash a password using BCrypt

Step 1: Install BCrypt library

```
$npm i bcrypt
```

- Step 2: Include bcrypt modules `Const bcrypt=required('bcrypt');`
- Step 3: set a value for saltRounds. Here we set values for saltRounds. Higher the saltRounds value, the more time the hashing algorithm takes.

```
Const saltRounds=12;
```

- Step 4: Declare a password variable `var password="Kasd^42t@jwe";`
- Step 5: generate a salt

You can salt and hash the password in one function or by using separate function. Here in genSalt fn, we pass `bcrypt.genSalt()` these parameters:

1. saltRounds
2. callback of error and returned salt:

```
bcrypt.genSalt(saltRounds,function(err,salt)
```

```
{  
    //returns salt  
}
```

- step 6: Hash the password we pass `bcrypt.hash()` these parameters:

1. password
 2. salt
 3. callback of error and the returned hash
- ```
bcrypt.gensalt(saltRounds(err,salt)
{
```

```
Bcrypt.hash(password,salt,function(err,hash)
{
 //return hash
 Console.log(hash);
});
}); [9]
```

### IV. CONCLUSION

For salting and hashing passwords, Bcrypt is a common and trusted approach. You have shown how to use bcrypt's NodeJS library to salt and hash a password before saving it in a database. Password protection is one of the essential part of security. Hashing is a technique that is commonly used to convert plain text passwords into a set of characters that cannot be decoded. In this paper we discussed about BCrypt which can be used to avoid these kind of security issues and provide more secure access.

### V. FUTURE WORKS

In future this can be used in many social websites in order to provide secure access to their users. This BCrypt makes any kind of data secure.

### VI. REFERENCE

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